

Polarographic Reduction of two Azo Dyes : DPP and SPADNS

WAHID U. MALIK^a, RAMESH BEMBI^b, R. N. GOYAL, OM PRAKASH TANDON and R. K. PALIWAL^c

Department of Chemistry, University of Roorkee, Roorkee

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DPP and SPADNS, two well known azo dyes give one well defined, 2-electron transfer, diffusion controlled, reversible cathodic wave up to pH 5.5, after which one more wave appears at lesser negative potential. This wave is due to the possible role of adsorption. After pH 5.5, the main wave also shows irreversible behaviour.

AZO dyes constitute an important class of mordant dyes used for dyeing of fibres¹. From the analytical view point also they are invaluable for trace analysis² of rare metals like zirconium, cerium, thorium etc. Although wide ranging studies have been carried out on the metal complexes of these dyes, little attention has been paid to their polarographic reduction. Two azo dyes DPP and SPADNS, having the structures given below, have therefore been studied polarographically.

Fig. 1.

Experimental

DPP and SPADNS were E. MERCK and LOBA CHEMIE AUSTRANAL products respectively. They were purified by crystallisation from 50% ethanol. After drying over silica gel, they were checked for their purity by paper chromatography.

Stock solutions ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$) of the dyes were prepared in doubly distilled water. They were studied polarographically in Walpole-Acetate buffer³,

(pH 2.0-5.5) and Britton Robinson buffers⁴ (pH 5.5-12.0). The pH of the buffers was checked with an Elico-LI-10 pH meter, using glass electrodes.

Fig.2.- Typical polarograms of dyes SPADNS (1-4) and DPP (5-8) at various pH ($C=1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$)

Polarographic curves were recorded at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ on a Cambridge pen recording polarograph using a Fischer Capillary having a capillary characteristic of $(m^2 t^{\frac{1}{2}}) = 1.5276 \text{ mg}^{\frac{2}{3}} \text{ s}^{-\frac{1}{2}}$. A saturated calomel electrode was used as reference electrode and 0.1 M KCl as supporting electrolyte. In the case of DPP, no maxima suppressor was used, while a freshly prepared gelatin solution (0.005%) was used in the case of SPADNS over the entire pH range studied.

In the case of DPP, 8.0 ml of buffer +1.0 ml of

(a) Present address : Bundelkhand University, Jhansi (U.P.)
(b) To whom all correspondence may be addressed.
(c) Department of Chemistry, Gurukul Kangri University, Haridwar.

The polarisation step (I) and step (III) are both known to be very rapid.

A similar mechanism has also been proposed by Zuman¹⁰ and others^{8,11,12} for other azo compounds.

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